

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component Bioinformatics PTPN6 (SHP-1)

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PTPN6 (protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 6), also called SHP1, is a member of the protein tyrosine phosphatase (PTP) family, expressed primarily in hematopoietic cells, and functions as an important regulator of multiple signaling pathways in hematopoietic cells. Phagocytosis of aggregated amyloid- β_{1-42} and bacterial particles were increased after knockdown of PTPN6 in microglia [4]. Knockout of CD33 as well as knockdown of the CD33 signaling-associated protein PTPN6 led to constitutive activation of inflammation-related pathways [4]. Aggregated α -syn binding to Fc γ RIIB on microglia and activating PTPN6, resulted in inhibited microglial phagocytosis. PTPN6 activation was also observed in A53T α -syn transgenic mice Parkinson's disease model [5].

PTPN6 is one of the marker genes for microglia. It mediates ITIM signaling downstream of CD33 and other Siglecs inhibitory pathways, while CD33 is a disease-associated microglia (DAM) marker gene and a highly ranked Agora nominated drug target. Functions reversely to LYN, which is another AD drug target proposed, PTPN6 dephosphorylates SYK, which in turn phosphorylates PLCG2 in microglia signaling. It also directly dephosphorylates LYN. In our recent GWAS study using ROSMAP cohort, PTPN6, along with three other genes including LYN, was found to be marginally associated with AD risk (p value 0.0659).

PTPN6 was identified together with other microglia drug target INPP5D, PLCG2, HCK, TYROBP, CSF1R in the core microglia coexpression module (AD3) only from AD patient brains of five AD brain transcriptomic datasets [1] and later on eight large AD transcriptomic datasets (Table-1). In a meta gene coexpression study [2], it was found to be coexpressed in consensus modules of immune response in TCX, FP, PHG, IFG, CBE and DLPFC region of the AD brain [2].

AD3_8Data_freq_0.05_unnormalized_0.74
ABI3, ARHGAP30, ARHGDIB, ARPC1B, BTK, C1QA, C1QB, C3, C3AR1, CD300A, CD74, CD86, CSF1R , CSF3R, CTSS, CYBA, CYBB, CYTL1, DOCK2, DOCK8, FCGR2A, FLI1, FPR1, GIMAP4, GIMAP6, GIMAP8, GPSM3, HAVCR2, HCK , HCLS1, HLA-DMB, HLA-DOA, HLA-DRA, IFI30, IL10RA, INPP5D , ITGAM, ITGB2, LAIR1, LCP1, LGALS9, LILRA2, LY86, MFNG, MS4A4A, MS4A6A, MS4A7, MYO1F, NCKAP1L, PIK3AP1, PLCG2 , PLEK, PTPN6 , PTPRC, RHBDF2, RNASE6, SERPINA1, SIPA1, SLA, SLC1A5, SLC2A5, SLC7A7, SLCO2B1, STK10, SYK, TAL1, TBXAS1, TLR2, TLR7, TMEM119, TREM2, TYROBP , VAV1, VSIG4, WAS, WDFY4

Table -1 Microglia core coexpression module AD3 from frequent coexpression network mining on eight large AD patient brain transcriptomic datasets.

In the bulk tissue differential gene expression analysis of multiple datasets, PTPN6 was found not to be differentially expressed [1]. However, in a single cell transcriptomic study [3], PTPN6 was found to be significantly upregulated in the excitatory neurons in MCI vs. normal and AD vs. Normal tissue comparison, but was not differentially expressed in other types of brain cells.

Gene Symbol	Cell Type	Data Source	log2_foldchange	Adjusted P value	Compare Status
PTPN6/SHP1	excitatory neurons	[3]	0.308914773	7.83E-03	pathology vs no-pathology
PTPN6/SHP1	excitatory neurons	[3]	0.254781374	1.5E-03	early-pathology vs no-pathology
PTPN6/SHP1	ROSMAP	[1]	0.2999	0.1025	pathology vs no-pathology
PTPN6/SHP1	MSBB	[1]	0.19111	0.2020	pathology vs no-pathology

In an epigenetic study of the H3K9acetylation ChIP-seq analysis of ROSMAP cohort, PTPN6 was found with increased acetylation on H3K9 site in the AD brain as compared to cognitive normal samples, which means an activation of the PTPN6 transcription (log2FC 0.0288, FDR 0.065). In our recent proteomic comparison, the LPS induced inflammation on mouse microglia BV2 cell vs. untreated BV2 cell line, PTPN6 protein level is significantly downregulated (log2FC -0.321, adjusted P 0.005). This is consistent with the previous finding that knockdown of PTPN6 led to constitutive activation of inflammation-related pathways in human microglia cell line [4].

In the PPI network, PTPN6 interacts with multiple AD drug target candidates such as INPP5D, TYROBP, IL10RA and STAT3 (Figure-1).

Figure-1 PPI network of PTPN6 from STRING.

Reference:

1. Johnson, T. et al. Combinatorial analyses reveal cellular composition changes have different impacts on transcriptomic changes of cell type specific genes in Alzheimer's Disease. *Sci Rep.* 2021 Jan 11;11(1):353. doi: 10.1038/s41598-020-79740-x.
2. Wan Y., et al. Meta-Analysis of the Alzheimer's Disease Human Brain Transcriptome and Functional Dissection in Mouse Models. *Cell Rep.* 2020 Jul 14;32(2):107908. doi: 10.1016/j.celrep.2020.107908.
3. Mathys H. et al. Single-cell transcriptomic analysis of Alzheimer's disease. *Nature*, 2019 Jun;570(7761):332-337. doi: 10.1038/s41586-019-1195-2.
4. Wißfeld, J. et al. Deletion of Alzheimer's disease-associated CD33 results in an inflammatory human microglia phenotype. *Glia.* 2021 Jun;69(6):1393-1412. doi: 10.1002/glia.23968. Epub 2021 Feb 4.

5. Choi Y. R. et al. FcγRIIB mediates the inhibitory effect of aggregated α -synuclein on microglial phagocytosis. *Neurobiol Dis.* 2015 Nov;83:90-9. doi: 10.1016/j.nbd.2015.08.025. Epub 2015 Sep 3.